

PSYCHOLOGY IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

Educational psychology is a fulfill knowledge for the teachers to help the students improve their learning in the English classes. Teaching in the English class is a profound and planned activity designed by the teacher to achieve specific goals. To achieve success in teaching, the teacher must have the necessary information and knowledge from the new educational theories and educational psychology. The purpose of this article is to show how a teacher who has more psychological knowledge is more successful than other instructors.

INTRODUCTION Psychology is the study and human's recognition from different dimensions of behavior and learning. In this article, we consider educational psychology and method teaching from the perspective of psychology. Educational psychology is trying to use the principles of psychology and its various branches in the field of education. In educational psychology, topics such as; different learning methods and its rules, the process of thinking, memorizing, remembering, memory, intelligence, motivation, measurement, the role of teachers and learners in the transfer of learning, the condition and situation of learning, discipline and academic achievement are considered and studied. On the other hand, the pedagogical significance is the consideration of the

impact of education, academic achievement, adaptability, mental development, and balanced human development.

The teachers should be aware of the application of educational psychology in a pedagogical system and can easily implement the principles and rules in the classroom. The students enter the class with difference significance; it is the teacher's duty to identify these differences and them according to their skills and abilities. Personal differences between the learners are one of the most important issues in the classroom that the teacher has to pay particular attention to them and the learning-teaching process is arranged that all learners can use it according to their mental fitness.

The teachers must be a good psychologist before they play the role of teacher. Attention to the teacher's role in the teaching process and its strengthening can be effective in learning the language. Teacher's awareness of the student's motivation and its relationship with the teaching process provides a framework by which the teacher can choose effective teaching methods to teach the English language to them. Logical education and principles are one of the effective factors in the teaching process. The characteristics that the teacher distinguishes from other educators is knowing the science of psychology and using it during the teaching. The Importance of Psychology in Teaching and Learning Educational psychology is a fulfill knowledge for the teachers to help the students improve their learning in the English classes. It doesn't matter a teacher teaches the English language at a school or at a university. In fact, teaching the English language as a second/foreign language is a difficult task. When a teacher manages the class who knew the educational psychology very well, he/she can be more successful in teaching than other instructors.

The first, the teacher attempts to create motivation in the class and attract the learner's attention to the subject. Lack of motivation is a major obstacle to the student's academic achievement, so all teachers' efforts to eliminate these obstacles and to provide an incentive for the class to learn more. Using visual aids in teaching the English language as a second/foreign language creates strong motivation between the learners and context which make it easier for them to learn new words in a target language and remember them forever. Motivation can be defined as a need or desire that energizes and directs

behavior. Motivation is a term which occurs in a discussion of the second rather than the first language learning. There are two types of motivation: intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. In a socio-educational aspect, motivation also can be defined as integrative motivation and instrumental motivation. An instrumental motivation means the desire to acquire a foreign language to find out employment or improve their self-cultivation or improve the social status. According to Tomlinson (2003), materials can include anything which can be used to facilitate learning of a language. Today, most learners are advocates of working with the internet, which, if the teacher uses of PowerPoint, some soft ware's in teaching the English language, the motivation of the learners to learn more. The second, a skillful teacher reduces the student's stress and anxiety, and strengthen their self-esteem. Occasionally, the learners face fear and stress in learning challenges, which reduces their self-esteem. Insufficient self-esteem takes their positive thoughts as a result, their performance will not be appropriate. So the teacher must recognize the root of these fears and stress and help the students to overcome them through appropriate strategies. Most students are afraid to speak in an English language class, they think that mocked by their classmates if they replace the words incorrectly in the sentence or express a word with a false pronunciation. The teacher should allow the learners to speak without tension even if they make a mistake in their words and created an intimate environment in the class which the learners can participate in the group discussions. The psychologists believe that the teacher should play the role of teacher-centered on the class and prevent any

anxiety and also patiently correct their mistakes.

An understanding of the individual differences of students and recognition of them in the work of teachers is very important and leads to the needs of the various students, and the teacher can discover and understand the various talents of the learners and help their learning. So teachers who have the knowledge of psychology and patiently and creatively motivated their learners and help them to succeed without anxiety are more successful teachers. Teaching English Vocabulary through Educational Psychology Knowledge English is known as an international language and is used as an international communication tool. Language is the only way of communication, even before the formation of human societies; people interacted together by engraving on the stones and walls. The learning of mother language is very important, but don't forget it if somebody doesn't learn an international language (English), they face many serious problems because technology and science are rapidly developing in the English language. The purpose of this article is to encourage the teachers to help the learner's speaking skills in English classes with the educational knowledge. There are several major problems related to lack of communication in the English class. Not only the teacher provides the student's mental condition and reduces their anxiety in the class, creating a comfortable atmosphere in the classroom and also motivates the learners, but the teacher should choose a teaching approach that isn't boring for students. The teachers should choose objectives that the students can realize within the parameters of the course activities and assignments.

Language students should understand that the teacher expects them to be able to use the material they are learning to speak to someone else. They should also know that the teacher expects them to participate in the foreign language in the class activities. Between the skills in learning English language, speaking plays several roles in language learning in the class. One of the most important roles of speaking is to serve as a vehicle for participating in class activities and also one of the greatest challenges facing language teachers is that of creating new and more productive ways to help students develop communication skills. Vocabulary is an indispensable part of the English language learning process. It would be impossible to learn a language without vocabulary. It is the primary skill which should be mastered by the children before they acquire another language skill, such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing. It means that vocabulary plays an important role in both spoken and written communication. All speaking activities should have some specific task for students to complete. The student's role in speaking activities involves affective, social, and cognitive factors. During the group activities, the teacher is responsible to manage the class; the teacher's role is like a stimulus that encourages students to act in the classroom. If the teacher wants to succeed in her work, she must attract the learner's attention and make a good relation with them. As a teacher attempted to make a good relation to the learners. For example, she requested the shy students to help another student in the role of teacher and involved them in a small group activity or they participated in the group activities with their friends. So, the learners could gain more than 80% of the mark in multiple-

choice questions. The result of this research shown that teaching the English language by educational psychology knowledge is undoubtedly the most successful teaching.

CONCLUSION

Most learners would like to learn to speak the English language, but developing speaking skills isn't easy. They attempt to learn this language as a foreign language that's why they looking for the best teacher who teaches them the English language in an appropriate class. Teaching English in a variety of countries, including in our country, faces many problems. Most teachers and students involved in the teaching-learning process many hours in the class, but they haven't had much success. Every teacher should have complete knowledge of educational psychology so that helps to the learners in

learning a foreign language. Understanding and identifying the desire, motivation, mental, and physical of the learners can help them learn more. The skillful teacher entered the shy children into the conversation and improved self-confidence of other learners in speaking skills of English language class. Therefore, the teacher's success is a fundamental principle and the attention of all teachers to the use of educational and behavioral methods should be prioritized. Aristotle says that the pride of teachers who teaches the students is more than those who create them. Good teachers are responsible for ensuring the success and progress of their students. For this reason, in this paper is highlighted the teacher's success depends on their psychological knowledge.

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